

Speculation of Special Relativity and Information

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Consider a mass at rest m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$. To an observer moving at a constant speed v , the values x and t are such that their ratio is $v=x/t$, but the mass now has momentum and a new energy. Yet the two scenarios represent the same information. In fact one may consider all constant v values as creating new representations of the same information state. This is like a rotation with a constant magnitude in linear algebra. x, t and v are chosen instead of $g_1(x)$, $g_2(t)$ and $g_3(v)$ for linearity. As noted, motion is directly linked to momentum and energy so one may postulate that not only does x, t behave like a rotation with fixed magnitude (dot product), but momentum and energy should be proportional to x and t with only constants and Lorentz invariants (i.e. a function of the dot product of x and t) as the proportionality factor.

x and t have different dimensions and in addition one still needs to define the dot product in terms of a metric. To do so we suggest comparing with light. This introduces c and the dot product form $xx - cctt$.

The above ideas may be used to obtain the form of special relativity namely $E = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$) and $p = Ev$. They are also linked to the inner product $-Et + px$ which is the classical Action for a free particle (relativistic or nonrelativistic) with t and x being treated as independent. By keeping this dot product constant one may also derive the form of special relativity i.e. $E = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$).

Frames of Reference and Information

Consider a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$. Next consider this same particle viewed from a frame moving at constant v . In such a case, the particle seems to have momentum, possibly a new energy and $x/t=v$. Yet there is one physical state so to speak, but many representations, each for a different v . Mathematically this seems to map into a rotation where each angle is linked to a different v , but the constant magnitude indicates there is an equivalence to all these vectors i.e. a constant inner product.

One may ask: Why should x , t and x/t be the variables of interest? Why could one not have $g_1(x), g_2(t)$ and $g_1(x)/g_2(t)$? We argue that this would be like considering a ruler with equal x spacings and two numbers written below each point, x and $g_1(x)$. x is linear while $g_1(x)$ is in general not and so we argue it is x which is a proper linear counting measure.

Next, one may consider that a stationary particle in a rest frame appears to be moving i.e. have momentum p and kinetic energy when viewed from the moving frame. Again one may argue that each v links to a rotated vector representing a different E and p . The basic state, however, at rest is a position time one (x, t) with m_0 as a parameter. Thus we argue that there is really no new information contained in the energy - momentum representation that is not already present in x, t and m_0 . As a result, we postulate that E, p should be proportional to t, x with various constants and Lorentz invariants i.e. the magnitude of the vector squared discussed.

Inner Product

In the previous section a constant inner product was discussed, but its specific form was not given. First there is the issue that x and t have different units and secondly a metric for the inner product is needed. Given that we argue that t, x is proportional to E, p for constant motion and that $E=pc$ for a photon, we consider x and ct as having the same dimension. In other words the ideas above for a particle with m_0 should link with a photon which has no m_0 , but has energy and momentum and is also moving in time and space. In fact a photon is said to have the same c when viewed from different frames when moving in a vacuum. We argue that this may be used to suggest an inner product:

$$(ct)(ct) - xx \text{ so that } (ct)(ct) - (ct)(ct)=0 \quad ((1))$$

With this metric one may return to the problem of the particle with rest mass m_0 .

Particle with Rest Mass

We argued in a previous section that E, p should be proportional to t, x with p and x both taking positive and negative values and E and t only positive. Furthermore x, t, E and p are countable. We suggest that $p=Ev$ by definition i.e. momentum means energy flow. For this to be proportional to x :

$$P = (t/t) E x/t \text{ so } E/t \text{ should consist of constants and Lorentz invariants} \quad ((2))$$

Thus: $t^* \text{ function}(x, t) = \text{Lorentz invariant}$.

We argued that the inner product of x, t is a Lorentz invariant because all different v vectors have the same magnitude and $v=x/t$. Thus:

$$\text{Constant} = xx - (ct)(ct) \quad ((3))$$

Then ((2)) suggests that:

$$E/t = \text{constant} / \sqrt{1-xx/tt} \text{ and } p = C1 v / \sqrt{1-vv} \quad ((4))$$

Similarly: $E = [\text{constant and Lorentz invariants}] t$ so $E = C2 / \sqrt{1-vv}$ is a solution ((5))

Finally, the inner product of p, E must be constant:

$EE - pp = \text{constant}$ For $v=0$, $C2=m_0$. This suggests $C1$ is also m_0 . Then:

$$E = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv} \text{ and } p = E v \quad (c=1) \quad ((5))$$

Thus the assumption of various x, t 's representing different velocities x/t and different rotational positions of a vector with a constant magnitude squared of $x^2 - (ct)^2$ and the idea that p, E is proportional to x, t with possible constants and Lorentz invariants seems to reproduce the form of special relativity.

Classical Action

It seems that the above ideas are linked to the classical action. Both the relativistic ($A = -m_0 c \int \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} dt$) and nonrelativistic $A = \int \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2 dt$ classical actions may be written with $v = x/t$ for a free particle and varied independently with respect to x and t . This yields:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \text{ and } dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \quad (6)$$

A solution is: $A = -Et + px$, but this is the inner product of (p, E) and (x, t) . (We already noted that (p, E) is proportional to (x, t)). An alternative approach shown in a previous note is that using $p = Ev$ and $dA = 0 = -dE/dv dt + dp/dv dx$ also leads to the form of special relativity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we use the idea of information to argue that a particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at $t=t_0$ is in essence the same as this system viewed from various frames moving at different constant velocities v such that $v = x/t$. This suggests mathematically that one has rotated x, t vectors, each one corresponding to a different constant velocity, but with a constant inner product which indicates that each represents the same essence or information. Furthermore we suggest that p, E should be proportional to x, t because momentum and $E(v)$ only emerge when the particle at rest is seen from a moving frame. In other words E, p do not represent new information from $m_0, x=0, t=t_0$.

We argue that one should link these ideas to a photon for which $E = pc$. We suggest using ct so that x and ct have the same dimensions and use $x^2 - (ct)^2$ as the constant inner product.

Applying this to the particle with rest m_0 , we find that for E and p to be proportional to x and t up to a proportionality constant made of m_0 and a Lorentz invariant one has:

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad (c=1) \text{ and } p = Ev.$$

Thus these ideas lead to the form of special relativity we argue. We also make the link with the classical action (relativistic or nonrelativistic) for a free particle which turns out to be $A = -Et + px$ with x and t independent. For $dA = 0 = -dE/dv dt + dp/dv dx$ and $p = Ev$ one may also derive the form of special relativity.